

MASNAVI IN MODERN UZBEK PROSE.

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As the writer makes a philosophical observation about human problems living in space and time through artistic interpretation, his comments about life are naturally based on cause and effect, purpose and essence. These aspects show the unique style of the writer.

Modern Uzbek prose has its own rich traditions and works of this literary type that are filled with examples of world artistic thinking. Freedom of creativity in the years of independence expanded the possibilities of our prose. Our writers courageously created magnificent works on historical topics; they freely created in all genres of prose both in traditional and new styles. More than two hundred novels, thousands of stories and short stories created during almost a quarter of a century testify to the potential of Uzbek prose in the period of independence.

Literary experts, writers, critics and researchers discussed many issues at the roundtable discussion called "Modern Uzbek prose: today and tomorrow" at the initiative of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. , argued. In particular, many topics such as the place of our prose in today's literary process, emerging literary-aesthetic trends, artistic interpretations of universal human problems, attitude to entertainment "market literature", creative experiences of young writers are part of the content of this roundtable discussion. Took the writer's position in the process of globalization, the growth and changes occurring in the life and thinking of our contemporaries, to what extent are reflected in today's research in prose, were the focus of the conversation.

Of course, just as it is impossible to fully comment on the active creative process, especially the achievements in prose, in a roundtable discussion, it is impossible to clarify the reasons for the shortcomings in this regard in detail.

In modern Uzbek literature, there are few, almost no, poets and writers who create in the form of masnavi. However, in the works and poetry of Abduqayum Yoldoshev, Ulug'bek Hamdam, Vika Asadchenko, Marat Bayzakov, Abdukakhhor Ibrohimov, Mirkarim Osim and others, there are works in the form of masnavi and aspects of traditionalism and innovation.

Masnavi (Arabic for "double") is not only a form of poetry, but also a genre of oriental literary work, one of the main forms of traditional Persian narrative work with an unlimited number of bayts, which are written in the form of

rhyming couplets. These are verses divided into independent, internally rhyming stanzas.

Most masnavi follow a meter of 11 (sometimes 10) syllables. and since the number of verses is not limited, the number of lines in a poetic work can reach up to 2000-9000. Jalal ad-Din Rumi's epic-didactic poem "Masnavi" and Nizami Ganjavi's poem "Iskander-name" were written in the Masnavi genre.

So, Masnavi is a kind of verse where the beit, that is, its two misrs, has a single rhyme, but the rhymes of different beits differ from each other, for example:

___a ___a
___b ___b
___c ___c

Masnavi rhyming scheme: aa - bb - cc...

The type of masnavi versification is used in spiritual-mystical, epic, moralizing and love works. Its appearance dates back to the reign of the Samanid dynasty. For example, 6 masnavi of a moral nature have come down to us from Rudaki. Unsuri owns 3 masnavi, one of which is the love story of Vamek and Azra. Asad Gurgani wrote "Vis and Ramin" - a love masnavi from the V century.

However, the masnavi forms of these creations are far from the original Navoi masnavi. For example: by analyzing Masnavi, it is possible to clarify the history of its writing and the reasons for Navoi's "exile" to Samarkand. The letter begins with the verses Hamd and Na't. He glorifies Allah by saying, "Alimeki, let there be no heresy, Azimeki, let there be no end". The One who is the companion of the settled people and the leader of the traveling vagabonds sent a taxman to the steppe and warned him of the risk:

Hazar is the helper of the poor,
The leader of the traveling party;
What a tax collector
The spirit deceived Tawakkul;
Let us make love like mine,
Do not worry about luck.

Tawakkul is to believe that all good and bad deeds are from God, to rely on God in all situations and actions, to consider oneself as an instrument of activity, and to deeply believe that things other than God are also from God. A person is capable of many things, but he must understand that all these actions are due to the power of Allah. God's will is the ruler of our will.

In addition, in classical literature, small poetic works with a plot and epics are called Masnavi. In Turkish literature, Masnavi form was used for the first time in

Yusuf Khos Hajibnk's work "Kutadgu bilig". The works of Durbekpint "Yusuf and Zulayha" and "Makhzan ul-asrar" by Heydar Khorazmiyamt were published in Masnavi. By the time of Navoi, Masnavi became the main genre of epic poetry. The main epic works of the great poet ("Khamsa", "Lison uttayr", etc.) were written in the M. genre.

Masnavi is also used in contemporary Uzbek poetry. For example, H. Olimjon's poem "Uzbekistan", G. Ghulam's epics "Ko'kan", "Owners Occupy [Egalari egallaganda]" and others.

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Thus, what is common to most masnavi works, even if their bayts are written in a different rhyme, is that in them the instructions are confirmed by the stories.

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